

Can money and schooling save you from COVID-19?

A study on socio-economic factors that contribute to Data 1 Deaths in the
United States in 2021

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January, 2023

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1. Introduction

COVID-19 pandemic has brought great loss to humanity. One of the biggest countries that play a central role in fighting the virus is the United States, a leading country in terms of economy and education. This study uses the data of COVID-19 deaths, personal income, education attainment, and population density at a state level. The income, education, and density variables are paired with the number of deaths to calculate the correlation P-value. The results indicate that low rate of education attainment significantly correlates with COVID-19 deaths. However, income and population density do not show any significant correlation with the COVID-19 death tolls.

There are numerous studies conducted to examine the relationship between socio-economic factors and COVID-19 deaths. Some studies used more complex indicators and methods at a more fine-grained level. Hawkins and his team (2020), for example, used the Distressed Communities Index (DCI) to analyze the US fatalities at a county level and came to a conclusion that lower education levels and greater percentages of black residents are strongly associated with higher rates of both COVID-19 cases and fatalities.

Amaratunga and her team (2022) specifically examines the deaths and evolution of COVID-19 in the 21 counties of New Jersey considering the socio-economic factors like population, percentage of elders in the population, percentage of low-income households, access to food and health facilities, as well as the distance to New York City. The team found that the evolution of Covid-19 in New Jersey was influenced by certain socio-economic factors, and the most important factors were population and distance to NYC.

In the same year, Stojkoski and his team conducted research on a larger scale. They analyzed the data from 105 countries under 28 variables, such as healthcare infrastructure, societal characteristics, economic performance, and demographic structure. The team found that each variable's ability to explain the COVID-19 infections or mortality varies between countries because of their heterogeneous features.

This study comes to the similar result with the works of Stojkoski and his team (2022) and Dhammika Amaratunga and her team (2022) in that there are no common socio-economic factors that could

explain the death trend in a big picture because there are exceptional characteristics in some states that hugely influence the norm.

2. Aims and Objectives

It is interesting to examine the correlation between COVID-19 deaths and the factors of income, education, and population density in the US in 2021. The data will be analyzed at a state level.

The study aims to answer to the following research questions:

- I. Are death tolls related to income, education, and population density?
- II. What are the characteristics of the states with the highest number of deaths?

The hypothesis of the study are as follow:

- I. Less income and education contribute to more deaths related to COVID-19.
- II. More populated states have more COVID-19 deaths.

3. Data

The data used in this study can be divided into 4 parts as follow:

3.1. Deaths

COVID-19 death data is collected from CDC (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention), the US' leading science-based, data-driven, service organization that protects the public's health.

3.2. Personal Income

Personal income data of each state in the US is provided by the Bureau of Economic Analysis (BEA). County and metropolitan area per capita personal income statistics are calculated by dividing population into personal income. BEA used Census population figures to calculate annual per capita personal income statistics for 2020 and 2021.

3.3. Education Attainment

Education attainment of the population of each state in the US is gathered from World Population Review. The data consists of two levels of education: high school or higher and bachelor degree or higher.

3.4. Population Density

To land in a more nuanced analysis, another important factor like the population density is taken into account. On the World Population Review website, the US Census Bureau's World Population Clock has calculated the number of population in each state in the US per year and come up with the population density information.

4. Methods

Microsoft Excel is used to normalize the death tolls and Tableau to visualize the data. The statistical measure to figure out the correlation between deaths and other variables is P-value.

5. Data Manipulation

5.1. Data Retrieval and Normalization

5.1.1. Data 1 Deaths

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P
1	submission_date	state abbrev	tot_cases	conf_cases	prob_cases	new_case	pnew_case	tot_death	conf_death	prob_death	new_death	pnew_death	created_at	consent_casi	consent_deaths	
2	3/11/2021	KS	297229	241035	56194	0	0	4851				0	3/12/2021 15:20	Agree	N/A	
3	12/1/2021	ND	163565	135705	27860	589	220	1907				9	12/2/2021 14:35	Agree	Not agree	
4	1/2/2022	AS	11			0	0	0				0	1/3/2022 15:18			
5	11/22/2021	AL	841461	620483	220978	703	357	16377	12727	3650	7	3	11/22/2021 12:00:00 AM	Agree	Agree	
6	05/30/2022	AK	251425			0	0	1252				0	05/31/2022 01:20:20 PM	N/A	N/A	
7	05/17/2020	RMI	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	05/18/2020 04:01:54 PM	Agree	Agree	
8	4/3/2020	ND	173			14		3				0	4/3/2020 16:22	Agree	Not agree	
9	9/4/2021	PR	173967	144788	29179	667	274	2911	2482	429	8	3	9/4/2021 00:00	Agree	Agree	
10	5/9/2021	PW	0			0	0	0				0	5/10/2021 14:15			
11	08/15/2022	NM	602931			1509	0	8318				6	08/16/2022 01:14:12 PM	N/A	Not agree	
12	1/1/2022	UT	636992	636992	0	0	0	3787	3635	152	0	0	1/3/2022 13:55	Agree	Agree	
13	5/1/2021	SD	122688			28	5	1967	1601	366	0	0	5/2/2021 14:13	N/A	Agree	
14	4/3/2021	OH	1024011	866822	157189	2293	552	18646	18646	0	0	0	4/4/2021 13:43	Agree	Agree	
15	10/16/2022	NHC	2908749	2452178	456571	5934	1266	42158	36503	5655	8	-1	10/17/2022 01:39:58 PM	Agree	Agree	
16	03/17/2022	GU	46695			45	70	341				0	03/18/2022 01:48:08 PM	Not agree	Not agree	
17	7/8/2020	OK	25217			1040	0	471	469	2	4	0	7/9/2020 00:00	Not agree	Not agree	
18	07/31/2020	ND	6602	6602	0	133	0	103				0	8/1/2020 14:38	Agree	Not agree	
19	8/11/2020	GU	449			15	0	5				0	8/12/2020 13:50	Not agree	Not agree	
20	02/25/2022	SD	235787			133	0	2802	2802	0	14	0	02/26/2022 02:15:52 PM	N/A	Agree	
21	07/26/2021	OK	475578	373929	101649	1028	264	7488	6379	1109	8	2	07/27/2021 02:48:23 PM	Agree	Agree	
22	05/20/2022	NY	2890549			6217	0	27790				17	05/21/2022 01:16:11 PM	Not agree	Not agree	
23	4/3/2022	OK	1034439	756298	278141	0	0	14010	9808	4202	0	0	4/4/2022 14:11	Agree	Agree	
24	09/23/2021	NYC	1075197	881626	193571	1755	168	34153	28965	5188	20	-7	09/24/2021 01:56:18 PM	Agree	Agree	

5.1.1.1. Download the .csv file from CDC website:

<https://data.cdc.gov/Case-Surveillance/United-States-COVID-19-Cases-and-Deaths-by-State-o/9mfq-cb36>.

5.1.2. Personal Income

	A	B	C	D
1		2019	2020	2021
2	United States	56,250	59,765	64,143
3				
4	Alabama	43,288	46,179	49,769
5	Autauga	42,846	45,248	48,347
6	Baldwin	48,380	51,348	54,659
7	Barbour	34,870	37,120	40,428
8	Bibb	31,800	34,598	36,892
9	Blount	36,542	38,351	42,634
10	Bullock	27,192	30,429	33,267
11	Butler	39,254	41,151	46,050
12	Calhoun	36,869	39,546	42,621
13	Chambers	33,682	36,299	39,728
14	Cherokee	37,751	39,416	43,719
15	Chilton	36,195	38,551	41,748
16	Choctaw	38,651	41,413	44,241

5.1.2.1. Download .xlsx file from the website

<https://www.bea.gov/data/income-saving/personal-income-county-metro-and-other-areas>. On the website under the Current Release, select the County Table to download the file.

5.1.2.2. In the excel file, remove text at the beginning and the end of the document keeping only the table with header.

5.1.2.3. Rename the file and header in Tableau to 'income'.

5.1.3. Education Attainment

education by states

state	PercentHighSchoolOrHigher	PercentBachelorsOrHigher
Montana	94	33.1000
Wyoming	93.6000	28.2000
Vermont	93.5000	39.7000
Minnesota	93.4000	36.8000
New Hampshire	93.3000	37.6000
Maine	93.2000	32.5000
Alaska	93.1000	30

5.1.3.1. Download the data .csv from the website

<https://worldpopulationreview.com/state-rankings/educational-attainment-by-state>.

5.1.4. Population Density

population density by states

rank	state	pop2022	growthRate	pop2021	pop2010	growthSince2010	percent	densityMi
1	California	39995077	0.0057	39766650	37253956	0.0736	0.1193	256.7424
2	Texas	29945493	0.0135	29545499	25145561	0.1909	0.0893	114.6318
3	Florida	22085563	0.0125	21811875	18801310	0.1747	0.0659	411.8520
4	New York	20365879	0.0041	20283564	19378102	0.0510	0.0607	432.1580
5	Pennsylvania	13062764	0.0023	13032732	12702379	0.0284	0.0390	291.9510
6	Illinois	12808884	-0.0001	12810696	12830632	-0.0017	0.0382	230.7117
7	Ohio	11852036	0.0022	11825742	11536504	0.0274	0.0353	290.0574

5.1.4.1. Download .csv file from the website

<https://worldpopulationreview.com/states>.

5.1.5. Full State Name and Deaths per 100,000

There are two points that have to be added and calculated in the death file: a full state name and normalized death per 100,000 persons per state. For the death file to be able to join and compare with other files (income, education, and population density), the state names have to be in full, and death figures need to be normalized.

5.1.5.1. First, get a list of abbreviations and full state names. It can be found through this link: <https://www.scouting.org/resources/los/states/>.

5.1.5.2. Copy the table of full and abbreviated state names and paste it in a new sheet in the death file.

5.1.5.3. In the abbreviation sheet, cut the 'state' column and paste it after the 'postal' column to be able to use vlookup function.

	A	B	C	D	E
1		Standard Postal	State		
2		Ala.	AL	Alabama	
3		Alaska	AK	Alaska	
4		Ariz.	AZ	Arizona	
5		Ark.	AR	Arkansas	
6		Calif.	CA	California	
7		C.Z.	CZ	Canal Zone	
8		Colo.	CO	Colorado	
9		Conn.	CT	Connecticut	
10		Del.	DE	Delaware	

5.1.5.4. In the death sheet, add a new column ‘state’ and change the existing ‘state’ column name to ‘state abbreviation’.

5.1.5.5. Use vlookup function in the newly created column to get a full state name.

	A	B	C	D
1	submission_	state abbrev	state	tot_cases
2	3/11/2021	KS	Kansas	297229
3	12/1/2021	ND	North Dakota	163565
4	1/2/2022	AS	American Samoa	11
5	11/22/2021	AL	Alabama	841461
6	05/30/2022	AK	Alaska	251425
7	05/17/2020	RMI	Republic of the Marshall Islands	0
8	4/3/2020	ND	North Dakota	173
9	9/4/2021	PR	Puerto Rico	173967
10	5/9/2021	PW	Palau	0
11	08/15/2022	NM	New Mexico	602931
12	1/1/2022	UT	Utah	636992
13	5/1/2021	SD	South Dakota	122688
14	4/3/2021	OH	Ohio	1024011
15	10/16/2022	NYC	New York City	2908749
16	03/17/2022	GU	Guam	46695
17	7/8/2020	OK	Oklahoma	25217

5.1.5.6. Next, we calculate normalized deaths by copying the ‘state’ and ‘pop2021’ columns from the population density file and putting them next to each other in a new sheet in the death file.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	rank	state	pop2022	growthRate	pop2021	pop2010	growthSince	percent	densityMi
2	1	California	39995077	0.0057	39766650	37253956	0.0736	0.1193	256.7424
3	2	Texas	29945493	0.0135	29545499	25145561	0.1909	0.0893	114.6318
4	3	Florida	22085563	0.0125	21811875	18801310	0.1747	0.0659	411.852
5	4	New York	20365879	0.0041	20283564	19378102	0.051	0.0607	432.158
6	5	Pennsylvania	13062764	0.0023	13032732	12702379	0.0284	0.039	291.951
7	6	Illinois	12808884	-0.0001	12810696	12830632	-0.0017	0.0382	230.7117
8	7	Ohio	11852036	0.0022	11825742	11536504	0.0274	0.0353	290.0574
9	8	Georgia	10916760	0.0095	10814334	9687653	0.1269	0.0326	189.8138
10	9	North Carolina	10620168	0.0086	10529778	9535483	0.1138	0.0317	218.4411
11	10	Michigan	10116069	0.0019	10096700	9883640	0.0235	0.0302	178.922
12	11	New Jersey	9388414	0.0053	9338704	8791894	0.0678	0.028	1276.6405
13	12	Virginia	8757467	0.0073	8694430	8001024	0.0945	0.0261	221.7642
14	13	Washington	7901429	0.0126	7803355	6724540	0.175	0.0236	118.8971

5.1.5.7. Then, since the date of submission in the death file is represented in days, but we need the data for the whole year of 2021 in each state, we use a pivot table to aggregate the dates into a year.

5.1.5.8. First, filter only the submission date in 2021 by selecting all cells with data in the death file, clicking Data>Filter, and in the ‘submission_date’ column, selecting only 2021.

5.1.5.9. Copy the whole table of 2021 deaths and paste it in a new sheet.

5.1.5.10. In the 2021 death sheet, select all and click insert > pivot table.

5.1.5.11. Put ‘state’ and ‘submission_date’ columns in ‘Rows’ field and ‘new_death’ in ‘Values’.

- 5.1.5.12. In the pivot table, right click a state name and select Expand/Collapse>Collapse Entire Field to see a state and the sum of deaths for the whole year.

	A	B
1		
2		
3	Row Labels	Sum of new_death
4	Alabama	4010
5	Alaska	210
6	American Samoa	0
7	Arizona	6539
8	Arkansas	2262
9	California	20687
10	Colorado	2361
11	Connecticut	1321
12	Delaware	520
13	District of Columbia	182

- 5.1.5.13. Copy the table and paste it in the sheet created in step 5.1.5.6. next to 'state' and 'pop2021' columns.
- 5.1.5.14. Now that we have state names, population, and deaths, we can normalize the deaths per 100,000 by multiplying the death with 100,000 and dividing it with the population. The calculation formula for Arizona in the second row, for example, would be =C2*100000/B2.

	A	B	C	D
1	state	pop2021	death	death per 100000
2	Arizona	7227450	6539	$=C2*100000/B2$
3	West Virginia	1787788	1592	89.04858965
4	Wyoming	578173	461	79.73392047
5	Alabama	5048733	4010	79.42586784
6	Arkansas	3021085	2262	74.87376224
7	Florida	21811875	16241	74.4594401
8	Georgia	10814334	7925	73.28236764
9	South Carolina	5167731	3782	73.18492391

5.1.5.15. Copy and paste the formula down along the whole column for all states.

5.1.5.16. Copy the whole table and save it as a new file.

5.2. Upload and Joining Tables in Tableau

The screenshot shows the Tableau interface. On the left, the 'Connections' pane lists several data sources, including 'Data 1 COVID...ths 2021.txt', 'Data 3 educati... by states.csv', and 'Data 4 populat... by states.csv'. The 'Files' pane shows options for using the Data Interpreter. In the center, a joining map shows 'Data 1 Deaths' as the primary table, with 'Data 2 Income', 'Data 3 education by state...', and 'Data 4 population density ...' joined to it. At the bottom, a data preview table is shown with columns for 'State', 'pop2021 (United States...)', and 'death'. The preview table contains data for Arizona, West Virginia, Wyoming, and Alabama.

State	pop2021 (United States...)	death
Arizona	7,227,450	
West Virginia	1,787,788	
Wyoming	578,173	
Alabama	5,048,733	

5.2.1. Upload all the files to Tableau using 'Add' next to 'Connections'. It is advisable to upload the death file first as it will be the main file when we join the table 'state' in the next step.

5.2.2. Under 'files', double click the relevant file names, and they will appear on the top right joining map.

5.2.3. Make sure to specify the joining column of each pair of the file under 'How do relationships differ from join?' header. The column in the main death file is 'State' with the operator '=', and select the state column in other files.

5.2.4. Open a new sheet. Tables on the left should show four files and the columns in each file.

Tables

- State
 - death
 - death per 100000
 - pop2021 (United_Stat...
 - Data 1 Deaths (Count)
 - F1
 - F2
 - F3
 - F4
 - Data 2 Income (Count)
 - state (Data 3 education...
 - Percent Bachelors Or H...
 - Percent High School Or...
 - Data 3 education by sta...

5.3. Creating Maps

First thing is to create a map to be able to visually compare each variable.

5.3.1. Death Map

(https://public.tableau.com/views/COVID-19DeathsandIncome/COVID-19Deaths2021?:language=en-US&publish=yes&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link)

- 5.3.1.1. On the left panel, double click to select 'state' and 'death per 100000'.
- 5.3.1.2. On the top right of the window, click Show Me and select the first map view on the second row
- 5.3.1.3. Under the 'Marks' module, click and drag 'death per 100000' from 'Tables' to 'Color' and 'Label'. Click and drag also 'State' to 'Label'.

- 5.3.1.4. On the right side of the map, click the triangle on the top right of the small window of SUM(Deaths) and select 'Edit Colors' to adjust colors and other parameters to make the visualization more distinctive.

5.3.2. Personal Income Map

(https://public.tableau.com/shared/X2TG4OSOX?:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link)

- 5.3.2.1. Open a new sheet.
- 5.3.2.2. Get the geographical data from Data 1 Deaths table. Under the table 'Data 1 Deaths', double click 'State'.
- 5.3.2.3. Repeat step 4.3.1.2. to 4.3.1.4 for 'Personal Income'.

5.3.3. Education Attainment Map

https://public.tableau.com/views/COVID-19DeathsandIncome/HighSchoolorHigher?:language=en-US&publish=yes&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link

https://public.tableau.com/views/COVID-19DeathsandIncome/BachelororHigher?:language=en-US&publish=yes&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link

5.3.3.1. In this step, we need to make two maps (one for each level).

5.3.3.2. Open a new sheet.

- 5.3.3.3. Under the table 'Data 3 Education by State', double click to select 'state' and 'Percentage High School or Higher'
- 5.3.3.4. Make sure that the 'Marks' for 'SUM(Percentage High school or Higher)' is 'color' to be able to visualize the color of each state by the percentage.
- 5.3.3.5. Click and drag 'Percentage High School or Higher' to 'Label' under 'Marks' module to show the percent numbers on the map.
- 5.3.3.6. Repeat the previous steps in a new sheet to make another map for the 'Percentage Bachelor or Higher'.

5.3.4. Population Density Map

https://public.tableau.com/views/COVID-19DeathsandIncome/PopulationDensity?:language=en-US&publish=yes&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link

- 5.3.4.1. Open a new sheet.
- 5.3.4.2. Under the table 'Data 4 Population Density', double click to select 'State' and 'Density MI'
- 5.3.4.3. Make sure that the 'Marks' for 'SUM(Density MI)' is 'color' to be able to visualize the color of each state by the percentage.
- 5.3.4.4. Click and drag 'Density MI' to 'Label' under the 'Marks' module to show the numbers of each state on the map.

6. Analysis

First, we need to make a list of 10 states with the highest death tolls to use as the main focal area when considering the other factors: income, education, and population density.

6.1. Top 10 Deaths

Top and Bottom 10 Deaths

Index	State	
1	Arizona	90.47
2	West Virginia	89.05
3	Wyoming	79.73
4	Alabama	79.43
5	Arkansas	74.87
6	Florida	74.46
7	Georgia	73.28
8	South Carolina	73.18
9	Tennessee	72.14
10	Montana	71.68

(https://public.tableau.com/views/COVID-19DeathsandIncome/TopandBottom10States?:language=en-US&publish=yes&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link)

- 6.1.1. Under the 'Tables' of 'Data 1 Deaths', double click to select 'state' and 'death per 100000'.
- 6.1.2. Click 'Show Me' on the top right of the window and select the 'Text Table' the first icon in the list.
- 6.1.3. Click and drag 'State' to the 'Filter' module. Click 'Edit Filter' and tick 'Null, Alaska, Hawaii, American Samoa, Guam, the Northern Mariana Islands, Puerto Rico, and the U.S. Virgin Islands' to exclude them from the table. Make sure to tick 'Exclude' on the bottom right.
- 6.1.4. Create an index number by right clicking an empty area in the 'Table' module and select 'Create Calculated Field'. Rename it to 'Index' and type 'index()' in an empty space below. Click 'OK'. Drag and drop 'Index' on the bottom of the 'Tables' module to 'Rows' in front of 'State'.

Index 2020-22 copy ×

Results are computed along Table (across).
`index()`

[Default Table Calculation](#)

The calculation is valid. 2 Dependencies ▾ Apply OK

6.1.5. Click the sort ascending or sort descending icons on the top panel to arrange the number of deaths in a descending order.

6.1.6. We can save the list as ‘Top 10 Deaths’ by selecting the top 10 state names while holding the ‘Shift’ key, right clicking, and selecting the third icon ‘Create Set’. Name it accordingly.

6.2. Deaths and Personal Income

According to the map, the bottom left side of the US saw a concentration of death tolls which is in accordance with the income map where people in the lower left part earn the least. However, this is not

fully applicable to the other parts like on the east side where a mix of death tolls and income are found. To confirm this observation, create another tab to calculate a correlation P-value between the two variables.

https://public.tableau.com/views/COVID-19DeathsandIncome/DeathsandIncome?:language=en-US&publish=yes&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link

- 6.2.1. To spot outliers, create a box plot by putting ‘income 2021’ and ‘death per 100000’ in ‘Rows’ and ‘state’ in ‘Columns’.
- 6.2.2. Click ‘Show Me’ and select ‘box-and-whisker plots’. We can see that Washington, Delaware, New York, and Ohio are the outliers of the ‘income 2021,’ and there are none for the ‘death per 100000’.

- 6.2.3. Next we continue to draw a correlation graph. Under the ‘Tables’ module, double click ‘state’ and ‘death per 100000’ under ‘Data 1 Deaths’, as well as ‘2021’ under ‘Income’ table.
- 6.2.4. On the top right, click ‘Show Me’ and select ‘scatter plot’ which is the first icon on the second to last row.
- 6.2.5. Make sure that ‘Sum’ and ‘Continuous’ are ticked for both variables.
- 6.2.6. Under the ‘Marks’ module, select the ‘Label’ icon in front of the name to display the state name.
- 6.2.7. We can see the names of the outlier states to be excluded.

Deaths and Income

- 6.2.8. On the ‘Analysis’ tab on the top window, select ‘Show Trend Lines’.
- 6.2.9. The P-value can be found by hovering the cursor over the trend line or right clicking the trend line and selecting ‘Describe Trend Line’.

Despite excluded outliers, there is no correlation between income and deaths nationwide (P-value = 0.73). In addition, the trend line suggests that the higher the income, the more deaths, which is the opposite of the hypothesis.

6.3. Deaths and Education Attainment

From the maps, a strong relation can be seen in the lower right and left parts where the number of the population with the education level is the lowest and the number of deaths are high. To confirm the observations, we create a graph and calculate P-value for both levels of education.

https://public.tableau.com/views/COVID-19DeathsandIncome/COVID-19DeathsandHighSchoolorHigher2?:language=en-US&publish=yes&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link

(https://public.tableau.com/views/COVID-19DeathsandIncome/COVID-19DeathsandBachelororHigher?:language=en-US&publish=yes&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link)

- 6.3.1. To make the correlation graph, open a new sheet.
- 6.3.2. Under the 'Tables' module, double click to select 'death per 100000' and 'state' under 'Data 1 Deaths' and 'Percentage High School or Higher' under 'Data 2 Education by State' table.
- 6.3.3. Repeat steps 6.3.3. - 6.3.6.

From both graphs, the hypothesis is confirmed for both levels: high school and higher, as well as bachelor and higher. The P-value < 0.0001 indicates a strong correlation between low education (not holding neither a high school nor bachelor diploma or higher) and deaths. West Virginia has a specially low number of people with a bachelor degree or higher (21.3%) and a relatively high death toll (89.05 deaths per 100,000).

6.4. Deaths and Population Density

Based on the maps, we can make two observations: the clusters of deaths in the southwest and the east correlate with the population density in that zone, but in some states like Washington, Colorado, and Texas, the death tolls are high despite low population density. We can prove the observations with a correlation graph. The initial graph drawing shows some outliers, so we need to sort them out using a box plot.

(https://public.tableau.com/views/COVID-19DeathsandIncome/COVID-19DeathsandPopulationDensity?:language=en-US&publish=yes&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link)

6.4.1. To spot outliers, create a box plot by putting ‘Density Mi’ and ‘death per 100000’ in ‘Rows’ and ‘state’ in ‘Columns’.

- 6.4.2. Click ‘Show Me’ and select ‘box-and-whisker plots’. We can see that New Jersey, Rhode Island, Massachusetts, Connecticut, Maryland, and Delaware are the outliers of the ‘Density Mi’.

- 6.4.3. Now, we create a correlation graph and exclude the outliers.
- 6.4.4. Open a new sheet.
- 6.4.5. Under the ‘Tables’ module, double click to select ‘death per 100000’ and ‘state’ under ‘Data 1 Deaths’ and ‘Density MI’ under ‘Population Density’ table.
- 6.4.6. Repeat steps 6.3.3. - 6.3.6.

Although outliers are already excluded from the graph, the P-value of 0.89 indicates no strong correlation between population density and deaths. There are many states on the lower right of the graph where the deaths are high despite low population density. These states are, for example, Arizona, Wyoming, Alabama, and West Virginia.

7. Results

7.1. Correlation between Variables

From the analysis of each pair of variables in the previous section, the results can be summarized as follow:

7.1.1. Deaths and personal income: no correlation (P-value = 0.73).

7.1.2. Deaths and education attainment

7.1.2.1. High school and higher: the lower rate of high school or higher educational attainment, the more deaths (P-value = 0.0001).

7.1.2.2. Bachelor and higher: the lower rate of bachelor or higher educational attainment, the more deaths (P-value < 0.0001).

7.1.3. Deaths and population density: No significant correlation found (P-value = 0.89).

The correlations confirm only the hypothesis on education attainment, while disproving the hypothesis about income and population density.

Since the US is a vast and diverse country with autonomous states that have their own regulations to handle COVID-19, it may be difficult to find out the common socio-economic factors contributing to COVID-19 deaths nationwide even though the outliers have been excluded. To be able to better see the patterns of socio-economic factors of each state, we can specifically narrow the scope down to the top 10 states based on death tolls and see if they share some characteristics, as well as which states are the exceptions that bend the norm.

7.2. Characteristics of Socio-economic Factors in Top States

State	Death per 100000	Income	Percent Bachelo..	Percent High Sc..	Density Mi
Arizona	1.00	44.00	30.00	38.00	32.00
West Virginia	2.00	51.00	50.00	40.00	29.00
Wyoming	3.00	6.00	39.00	2.00	49.00
Alabama	4.00	50.00	43.00	44.00	27.00
Arkansas	5.00	14.00	48.00	41.00	35.00
Florida	6.00	33.00	29.00	34.00	8.00
Georgia	7.00	43.00	24.00	38.00	17.00
South Carolina	8.00	47.00	36.00	36.00	19.00
Tennessee	9.00	40.00	39.00	37.00	20.00
Montana	10.00	39.00	19.00	1.00	48.00

(https://public.tableau.com/views/COVID-19DeathsandIncome/Rank2?:language=en-US&publish=yes&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link)

7.2.1. Open a new sheet.

7.2.2. Under the 'Tables' module, double click to select

- 'death per 100000' and 'state' under 'Data 1 Deaths' table,
- 'Income' under 'Data 2 Income' table,
- 'High School or higher' and 'Bachelor or Higher' under 'Data 3 Education by State' table, and
- 'Density Mi' under 'Population Density' table.

7.2.3. In the 'Measure Values' module, right click each variable, go to 'Quick Table Calculation', and select 'Rank'. Now, each variable is ranked depending on their value.

7.2.4. Sort the rank of deaths by clicking on the 'deaths per 100000' column header and selecting sort ascending.

Based on the ranking table, we will focus on the values that are particularly high or low in ‘income’ and ‘density’. In other words, we want to examine the exceptions that render the results deviate from the hypotheses. In the income column, Wyoming and Arkansas seem to weigh in the opposite side of the rest of the states (ranked 6th and 14th respectively). The population in the two states makes the 6th and 14th highest income compared with other states but still loses their lives to COVID-19. For population density, Montana and Wyoming are the least populated states (ranked 48th and 49th respectively) in the top 10 highest deaths.

Montana and Wyoming have some common characteristics. First, they are in the top 10 states with the highest deaths. Moreover, both states have the 1st and 2nd highest percentage of graduates from high school or higher and also the 1st and 2nd lowest population density.

8. Summary and Discussion

The ranking list further confirms that there are no common socio-economic factors that contribute to the COVID-19 deaths in the whole country of the USA in 2021. While most states share the same tendencies, some states have their own exceptions which are enough to affect the correlation between such variables and deaths. The only hypothesis which is confirmed by the result is that the states with low percentage of graduates from high school and bachelor degree or higher tend to have high deaths from COVID-19.

It would be interesting to analyze the data at a county level, which will reveal the correlation more accurately and in a more fine-grained fashion. Additionally, it would be interesting to take other socio-economic factors like age and gender into account. Last but not least, multiple-variable regression would bring this study further in terms of the analysis.

Lastly, we must not neglect the fact when calculating and analyzing the figures that behind these numbers there are actual losses. They are members of a family: a mother, a father, or a child. They are dear friends who are unfortunate during this pandemic. Upon the completion of this article, I would like to express my deepest condolences to the losses due to COVID-19 pandemic.

9. References

- Amaratunga, D., Cabrera, J., Ghosh, D. et al. Socio-economic impact on COVID-19 cases and deaths and its evolution in New Jersey. *Ann Oper Res* 317, 5–18 (2022).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-021-03941-4>.
- DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5195/jmla.2016.75>. Tableau. Technical specifications [Internet]. Seattle, WA: Tableau Software [cited 13 Oct 2020].
- Hawkins, R. B., Charles, E. J., & Mehaffey, J. H. (2020). Socio-economic status and COVID-19–related cases and fatalities. *Public health*, 189, 129-134.
- Stojkoski, V., Utkovski, Z., Jolakoski, P. et al. Correlates of the country differences in the infection and mortality rates during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic: evidence from Bayesian model averaging. *Sci Rep* 12, 7099 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-10894-6>.